

Molecular Characterization of Lactic Acid Bacteria Isolated from locally produced 'nono' in owo Iga, Ondo State, Nigeria.

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ABSTRACT:

Lactic acid bacteria (LAB) were isolated from locally produced 'nono' samples from three different locations in Owo, Ondo State (South Western Nigeria). Microbiological analysis was carried out using serial dilution and pour plate method for the isolation. The Agar used was De Mann Roggosa Agar (MRS) Oxoid, Nutrient Agar and Nutrient Broth (Oxoid). Four (4) species of (LAB) were mostly present in the "Nono": *Lactococcus lactis*, *Lactobacillus plantarum*, *Lactobacillus casei* and *Enterococcus faecalis*. Further identification at the species level indicated that all the lactococci isolates were *L. lactis* while three isolates of the *Enterococci* were *Enterococci faecalis* and *lactobacilli* were identified as *Lactobacillus plantinum* (1 Isolate). *Lactobacillus casei* (2 Isolates). PCR – RFLP method which is based on the amplification of 16s rRNA – ITS genes was used for the molecular characterization.

Keyword: "Nono", Lactic Acid bacteria, molecular characterization.,

INTRODUCTION:

"Nono", 'Nunu', in English language and Hausa Language is a spontaneously fermented yoghurt – like product, produced and consumed in some parts of West Africa (Akabanda *et al.*; 2014) unlike other fermented milk products where milk of goats, sheep and camels is used. Nono is solely prepared from Cow milk. It is yoghurt like in taste (a sharp, acid taste) and it can be taken alone or with "fura" (Owusu – kwarteng *et al.*, 2012; Akabanda *et al.*, 2013).

turning the product sour within few days. Milk nutritional composition makes it not only suitable for human nutrition but also ideal for microbial life (Nebedum and Obiakor, 2007; Paula, 2014)

MILK COMPOSITION: Milk is a white fluid secreted by female mammals for the purpose of rearing their offspring (O'Connor, 1993). The earliest tribes of ancient Egypt and south-west Asia discovered sometime around 5000BC that cow milk was a nourishing human food. While the ancient Egyptians recognized that cow was a wholesome and sustaining food they had little knowledge of its composition. The earliest evidence of knowledge of the composition of milk

Predominantly, "Nono" is being hawked by the nomadic Hausa or Fulani women, who control over 80% of Nigerian's cattle production (Obi and Ikenebomeh, 2007; Adesokan *et al.*, 2011). Nono contains good quantities of amino acids, calcium, phosphorus and vitamins A, C, E and B complex (Nebedum and Obiakor, 2007).

"Nono" is processed by collecting fresh Cow milk and allowing it to ferment for a day or two (Akabanda *et al.*, 2014). Raw milk has low keeping quality and at room temperature spontaneous microbial spoilage occurs is dated back to 350BC when Aristotle wrote that casein, fats and water are all the known substances of milk. Since the middle of the 19th Century knowledge of the Chemistry of milk has been developed and today there is extensive literature on the chemistry of the major and minor constituents of milk especially cow milk, variations exist in the composition of milk and for the various species of these animals.

The composition of Cow milk varies for a number of reasons e.g. individuality of the cow, the breed, age, stage of lactation, health of the cow, climatic conditions and herd management which includes feeding and general care. (Silanikove and Merin, 2016)

Table 1: Proximate composition of milk from various species of mammals

ANIMAL	COW	GOAT	EWE	CAMEL	BUFFALO
Fat	3.75	6.0	9.0	3.0	6.0
Casein	3.0	3.3	4.6	4.5	3.8
Lactose	4.75	4.6	4.7	5.5	4.5
Albumin	0.4	0.7	1.1	1.7	0.7
Ash	0.75	0.84	1.0	1.5	0.75
Water	87.3	94.4	79.6	84.8	85.0

Source: Connor, 1993.

Fermentation is the conversion of sugar into organic acid or an alcohol. Fermentation occurs naturally in many foods and humans have intentionally used it since ancient times to improve both the preservation and organoleptic properties of food. (Zhony, 2011). However, the term “fermentation” is also used in a broader sense for the intentional use of microorganisms such as bacteria, yeast, and fungi to make products useful to humans (biomass, enzymes, primary and secondary metabolites, recombinant products and products of biotransformation) on an industrial scale (Willaert and Neclovic, 2006).

Fermentation is also a term used by microbiologists to describe any process for the production of a product by means of the mass culture of a microorganism (Mitchell *et al.*, 1999). The product can be either the cell itself (biomass production) or microorganisms metabolite or products.

LACTIC ACID BACTERIA: Generally Lactic acid bacteria (LAB) can be defined as Gram positive, non – spore forming, catalase negative devoid of cytochromes, acid tolerant and facultative anaerobe group that produce lactic acid as the major end product during fermentation of carbohydrate (Cisem, 2000). According to carbohydrate metabolism, they can be divided into two main groups:

(1) Homo fermentative lactic acid bacteria produce mainly lactic acid.

(2) Heterofermentative lactic acid bacteria produce lactic acid, carbon-dioxide, ethanol and others.

This classification originated from metabolic routes that these organisms used and the resulting end-products. While homofermentatives use glycolysis (Embeden-Meyerhof pathway) heterofermentatives use the 6 –phosphogluconate or phosphoketolase pathways (Doo Hyun, 2018)

Although LAB comprises of eleven genera, only six of them are dairy associated. These are Lactococcus, Enterococcus, Pediococcus and Lactobacillus (De Martins *et al.*; 2011; Erich *et al.*; 2018). Dairy microflora is further divided into two groups. Primary group includes starter flora which refer to starter LAB and secondary group includes non starter lactic acid bacteria (NSLAB), propionic acid bacteria (PAB) smear bacteria, moulds and yeast (Beresford *et al.*, 2001).

MOLECULAR IDENTIFICATION OF LACTIC ACID BACTERIA: Identification of bacteria isolated from natural microflora involved in milk fermentation has been limited by the complexity of the bacteria association (Garvie, 1984). Additionally, bacterial population involved has similar nutritional and environmental requirements. As a result, the application of molecular methods can be used to resolve identification problems. Nucleic acid probe technology could be an alternative for faster and more reliable differentiation. Several species – specific probes have also been designed.

Furthermore, 16s or 23s rRNA targeted *oligonucleotide* have been used for the specific identification of lactic acid bacteria (LAB). Hence it is now possible to identify various lactic acid bacteria in fermented food without cultivation step at species level within one day (Scheifer and Ludwing, 1995). Additionally, DNA restriction fragment analysis and ribotyping have been used to distinguish Lactic acid bacteria (LAB), especially polymerase chain reaction based methods (PCR – RFLP, REP – PCR, PCR ribotyping and RAPD). Pulse field gel electrophoresis can be used as main molecular tools (Farber, 1996 and olive, 1999).

TABLE 3: Procedural steps of main genotypic methods

RAPD	PFGF	REP – PCR	AFLP	DNA Sequencing
PCR Amplification With single Primer	Embedded Organisms in Agarose plug	PCR Amplification With REP or ERIC primers	R.E. Disgestion	PCR Sequencing Reactions
↓	↓	↓	↓	↓
Gel Electrophoresis	Protease Digestion	Gel Electrophoresis	Linker Ligation	Gel Electrophoresis
↓	↓	↓	↓	↓
Gel Staining	R.E. Digestion	Gel Staining	Selective PCR	Computer aided Sequence analysis
↓	↓	↓	↓	↓
Interpretation	Electro – phoresis	Interpretation	Gel E. Through an Automated DNA Sequencer	↓
	↓		↓	↓
	Interpreta – tion		Gel Interpretation	Interpretation

Source: Cisem, 2003.

LACTIC ACID FERMENTATION

Fermentation is an energy yielding microbial metabolism in which an organic substrate usually carbohydrate is incompletely oxidized and an organic carbohydrate acts as the electron acceptor (Adams, 1990). Fermentation is either because “they lack an electron transport chain (Nester *et al.*,

2004), they lack the ability to respire; they only ferment, regardless of the presence of oxygen (O₂)” (Nester *et al.*, 2004). They can grow in the presence of oxygen but never use it as terminal electron acceptor. This is why they are sometimes called obligate fermentors (Nester *et al.*, 2004).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

SOURCES OF MATERIALS: Freshly prepared Nono were obtained from Fulani hawkers from three different locations; Iyere, Oke- Ogun and Ikare junction in Owo, Ondo State. Three samples were collected from each of these locations in an ice-packed and the samples were taken to the laboratory for microbiological analysis.

PREPARATION OF CULTURE MEDIA

The media used are De Man Rogosa and Sharpe, (MRS), M17 Agar and broth (Oxoid) for isolation of Lactic acid bacteria. The culture media were prepared according to manufacturer's instructions and sterilized in the autoclave at 121°C and 15psi for 15 minutes.

Microbiological analysis: Serial dilution was carried out using the sample and pour plate method was used. The Agar used were De Mann Roggosa Agar (MRS) Oxoid, Nutrient Agar and Nutrient Broth (Oxoid) .Enumeration and identification was carried out by total viable count while morphological characterization using colour, texture shape and size of the isolate while biochemical characterization were carried out using catalase Urease, Coagulase and sugar fermentation on the isolates for identification.

BACTERIAL IDENTIFICATION:The various bacteria colonies were sub – cultured to obtain pure culture. The isolates were coded and maintained on an MRS Agar slants and stored at refrigerated temperature. They were identified based on colonial, morphological, biochemical and genotypic characteristics.

MOLECULAR CHARACTERIZATION:

Extraction of DNA using CTAB method:Bacteria isolates grown overnight was transferred to eppendorf tube and it was spun down at 14,000rpm for 2mins, the supernatant was discarded and 600µl of 2X CTAB buffer was added to the pellet and it was incubated at 65°C for 20mins according to Akinyemi and Oyelakin 2014. The sample was removed from the incubator and allowed to cool to room temperature and chloroform was added, the sample was mixed by gentle inversion of the tube several times. Thereafter, the sample was spun at 14,000rpm for 15mins and the supernatant was transferred into a new eppendorf tube and equal volume of cold Isopropanol was added to precipitate the DNA. The sample was kept in the freezer for 1hr and later spun at 14,000rpm for 10mins and the supernatant was discarded and the pellet was washed with 70% ethanol, later the sample was air dried for 30mins on the bench. The pellet was re-suspended in 100ul of sterile distilled water. DNA concentration of the samples was measured on spectrophotometer at 260nm and 280nm and the genomic purity were determined. The genomic purity was between 1.8 –2.0 for all the DNA samples.

DNA Electrophoresis

Agarose gel electrophoresis was used to determine the quality and integrity of the DNA by size fractionation on 1.0% Agarose gels. Agarose gels were prepared by dissolving and boiling 1.0g Agarose in 100ml 0.5X TBE buffer solutions. The gels were allowed to cool down to about 45°C and 10µl of 5mg/ml ethidium bromide was added, mixed together before pouring it into an electrophoresis chamber set with the combs inserted. After the gel has solidified, 3µl of the DNA with 5µl sterile distilled water and 2µl of 6X loading dye was mixed together and loaded in the well created. Electrophoresis was done at 80V for 2 hours. The integrity of the DNA was visualized and photographed on UV light source.

PCR analysis using I6S primer PCR analysis was run with a universal primer for bacteria called 16S. The PCR mix comprises of 1µl of 10X buffer, 0.4µl of 50mM MgCl₂, 0.5µl of 2.5mM dNTPs, 0.5µl 5mM forward primer, 0.5µl of 5mM

reverse primer, 0.05µl of 5units/µlTaq with 2µl of template DNA and 5.05µl of distilled water to make-up 10µl reaction mix.

The PCR profile used is initial denaturation temperature of 94°C for 3mins, followed by 30 cycles of 94°C for 60sec, 56°C for 60sec, 72°C for 120sec and the final extension temperature of 72°C for 5mins and the 10°C hold forever.

Purification of PCR products

The amplicon is further purified before the sequencing using 2M Sodium Acetate wash techniques. To about 10µl of the PCR product, add 1µl 2M NaAct pH 5.2, followed by 20µl absolute ethanol, keep at -20°C for 1hr, spin at 10,000rpm for 10 minutes, then wash with 70% ethanol and air dried. Re-suspended in 5µl sterile distilled water and keep at 4°C for sequencing.

PCR for sequencing

The primer used for the reaction was forward I6S. The PCR mix used includes 0.5µl of Big Dye Terminator Mix, 1µl of 5X sequencing buffer, 1µl of M13 forward primer with 6.5µl Distilled water and 1µl of the PCR product making a total of 10µl. The PCR profile for sequencing is a rapid profile. The initial Rapid thermal ramp to 96°C for 1min followed by 25 cycles of rapid thermal ramp to 96°C for 10 seconds, rapid thermal ramp to 50°C for 5 seconds and rapid thermal ramp to 60°C for 4 minutes, then followed by rapid thermal ramp to 4°C and hold forever.

Purification of PCR sequencing products

The PCR sequence product is also purified before the sequencing running using 2M Sodium Acetate wash techniques. To 10µl of the PCR product add 1µl 2M NaAct pH 5.2, then add 20µl absolute ethanol, keep at -20°C for 1hr, spin at 10,000rpm for 10 minutes, then wash with 70% ethanol and air-dried. Re-suspend in 5µl sterile distilled water and keep at 4°C for sequencing running.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The total bacterial growth on MRS Agar ranges between 4.2x 10⁵ and 20x 10⁵ CFU/ml and total bacterial growths on M17 agar ranges between 3.0x10⁵CFU/ml and 10x10⁵CFU/ml as shown in Table 1 below:

Table 1: Total Bacterial Counts in Nono Samples from Three Agars Used

SN	SAMPLES LOCATION	MEDIA MRS AGAR	USED MI7
1a	GRA(Housi ng,Owo)	20x10 ⁵ CFU/ml	10x10 ⁵ CFU/ml
2b	Ikare	4.2x10 ⁵ CFU/ml	3.0x10 ⁵ CFU/ml
3c	Junction. Iyere (Owo)	4:5x10 ⁵ CFU/ml	3:5x10 ⁵ CFU/ml

RESULT OF GENE SEQUENCING 01

GATCCGTCTTAGGTGACATGGCTCAGGTGCGCTTGGT
CACCCCCTTAGAGTTTGAGCGGGCTCGCTTGGCTGT
GTCTGGCCTCTGCCTGATGGAGGGGGATAACTACTGG
AAACGGTAGCTAATACCGCATAACGTCGCAAGACCA
AAGAGGGGGACCTTCGGGCCTCTTGCCATCGGATGTG
CCCAGATGGGATTAGCTAGTAGGTGGGGTAATGGCTC
ACCTAGGCGACGATCCCTAGCTGGTCTGAGAGGATGA
CCAGCCACACTGGAAGTGGAGACACGGTCCAGACTCCT
ACGGGAGGCAGCAGTGGGGGAATATTGCACAATGGGC
GCAAGCCTGATGCAGCCATGCCGCGTGTATGAAGAA

GGCCTTCGGGTTGTAAAGTACTTTCAGCGAGGAGGAA
GGCATTGTGGTTAATAACCACAGTGATTGACGTTACT
CGCAGAAGAAGCACCGGCTAACTCCGTGCCAGCAGC
CGCGGTAATACGGAGGGTGAAGCGTTAATCGGAATT
ACTGGGCGTAAGCGCACGCAGGCGGTCTGTAGTCAG
ATGTGAAATCCCCGGGCTCACCTGGGAACTGCATTGA
ACTGACAGCTTGAGTCTATGTAAGAGGGGGGGTAGAT
TCAGGTGTAGCGGGTGAATGCTAGAGATCTGGAGATA
CTGGTGGCGGAGGGCCGCCTCCTGACAAAGACTGAC
GCCTCAGGTGCAAAGTCGTGGGGGAGCAACATGATA
AGATACCTGTAGTCACGCCGTAACGAGTCCACTGGA
GGTGGCCTTGAGGCGTGGCTCGACTTACCGTTAGTCC
ACCGCTGGGAGATACGCCAAGGTAATAATCAATGATT
GCCGGCTAGA

[Streptococcus
sp.6151](#) [CP046557.1](#)
[Streptococcus sp.
J807](#) [CP046446.1](#)

02
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GGGGGACCGCCCCTAATAAAGAATAATCTGTTTCACC
TCATGGTGAAATATTGAAAGACGGTTTCGGCTGTCCG
TATAGGATGGGCCCGCGGCATTAGCTAGTTGGTGA
GGTAACGGCTCACCAAGGCGACGATGCGTAGCCGAC
CTGAGAGGGTGATCGGCCACACTGGGACTGAGACAC
GGCCAGACTCCTACGGGAGGCAGCAGTAGGGAATC
TTCCACAATGGGCGAAAGCCTGATGGAGCAACGCCG
CGTGAGTGAAGAAGGATTTTCGGTTCGTAACACTCTGT
TGTAGGGAAGAACAAGTACAGTAGTAACTGGCTGTA
CCTTGACGGTACCTTATTAGAAAGCCACGGCTAACTA
CGTGCCAGCAGCCGCGTAATACGTAGTGGCAAGCGT
TGTCCGGGAATTATTGGCGTAAAGCGCGCGCAGGTGG
TTTCTTAAGTCTGATGTGAAGCCCCACGGCTCACCGT
GTAGGTCATTGCAACTGGGAGACTTACGTGCAGAGAG
GATAGTGATTCCAGTGTAGCGGTGAATGCGTAGAGAT
TGGAGACACAGTGCAGCGACTATTCTGGTCTGTACT
GACACTGAGGCGGAAAGCGTGGGAGCAACAGATAG
ATACCTGTAGTCCACGCGTTACGATGGAGTGCTAGTG
TAGGGCTTCGCTCCTTAAAGTGTGCTGACGCTTACGCATA
GCATCCGCTGGGGAATACGTTCTAGACTGAATCCTC
AAGGGAT

[Lactobacillus lactis strain
HCC](#) [KX908104.1](#)
[Lactobacillus casei. strain
TC3.1](#) [MK078608.1](#)

03
GGTTTAGTCTTATAACTGACATGGCTCAGGTGCGTTG
GACCACCTCTTTATAGTTTACGGCGGACGGGTGAGT
AACACGTGGCTCCCTGCCTGTAGACTGGGATAACTCC
GGGAAACCGGGCTAATAACCGGATGGTTGTTTGAACC
GCATGGTTCAAACATAAAAGGTGGCTTCGGCTACCAC
TTACAGATGGACCCGCGGCATTAGCTAGTTGGTGA
GGTAACGGCTCACCAAGGCAACGATGCGTAGCCGAC
CTGAGAGGGTGATCGGCCACACTGGGACTGAGACAC
GGCCAGACTCCTACGGGGAGGCAGCAGTAGGGAAT
CTTCCGCAATGGACGAAGTCTGACGGACAACGCCGCG
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TTAGGGGAGAACAAAGTACCGTTCGAATAGGGGCGGT

ACCTTGACGGTACCTAACCAGAAAGCCACGGCTAACT
ACGTGCAGCAGCCGCGGTAATAACGTAGTGGCAAGC
GTGTCGGAATTATTGGGCGTAAGGGCTCGCAGCGTTC
TAAGTCTGATGTGAAGCCCCGGCTCACGGGGAGGTCA
TGGAACTGGGAACTGGATGCGGAGAGGGGAGGGGAAT
TCCACTGTACGTGAATGCTAAAGATGGAGAACCATGG
CAAGCACTCTGTCTGAACTGACTAGCAACGTGGAGCC
TGATAGATCTGGATCCAGCTAACGATGCCTAGTGAGG
ATCCGCTTAGTCGCGAAGCCTAGGCCTCTCCGGAGAT
CGTCAAAAAA

[Lactobacillus lactis](#) [AY971358.1](#)

[Lactobacillus sp.](#)

04
GGATCAATTCTAGGATTGTCATGGCTCAGGTGCGCTT
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GTGGAGCCCCCTTTTAAATTGGTTGTTTGAACCCGTG
GTTCAAAAAAAGATTCGGCTACCACTTACA
GATGGGCCCGCGGCGCATTATCTAGTTGTGGAGGTAA
TGGCTACCAAGGCAACAATGCGTAGCCGACCTGAG
AGGGTGATCGCCACACTGGGACTGAGACACGGCCC
ACACTCCTATGGGGGGGGGAGTAGGGAATCTTCTCC
AATGGGCGAAAGTCTGTGCGGAGCAACGCCCCGTGAG
TGATGAAGTTTTTCTGATCTTAAAGCTCTGTTGTTAG
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TGAGGGTACCCTATCCAAAAGCCCCGGCTAAATACG
TGCCACCACCCCGGTAATACGTAGGGGGCAAGCGTT
GTCCGGAATTATTTGGGCGTAAAGGGCTCGCAGGCGG
TTCCTTTAGTCTGATGTGAAAGCCCCGGCCTCACCC
CGGAGGGTCTTTGAAACTGGGAACTTTAGTGCGG
AGAAGAGAAGGGATTTCCCTGTGTACGTGAAAGGC
GTAAGATTTGAGAGAACACCCGTGGCAAGGGCATCTT
TTGTCTGTAATCACGCTGAGGAGCGAAAACCTGTGGT
AGCGACAGGATATATACCCCTGTAATCCACAGCCGCT
AACGAAGAAGTGCTAACTGTTAGGAGTTTCCGCCCC
TTAGTGCTGCAAGATACGCGATTAATATGACATCGCT
CTTGGGAGAGTAATCGTCTGTTCTGTCTAGAGACTCGA
TTGAACACTCATTCAAGAGAATGT

[Lactobacillus lactis strain
IARI-CS-49](#) [JF343143.1](#)
[Lactobacillus sp. VP 18](#) [HM150753.1](#)
[Lactobacillus sp strain
SRR21 e](#) [KY401500.1](#)

05
GGTTTAGTCCAGGTGCGACATGGCTCAGGGGCGGTGGG
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ATGGTTCAAATTTGAAAGGAGGCTTCGGCTGTCACTT
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TAACGGCTCACCAAGGCAACGATGCGTAGCCCGACCT
GAGAGGGTGATCGGCCACACTGGGACTGAGACACGG
CCCCAGACTCCCTACGGAGGGAGCAGTAGGGAATCTT
TCCGCAATGGACGAAAAGTTCTGACGGAGCAACCCCC
CCCGTGAGGTGATGAAGGCTTTTCGGGGTCAAAAAC
TTCCGGTTGGTTAGGGGAAAAAACAATTGCTAGTTT
GGAATAAGGCTGGCCACCTTGGGACGGGTACCCTAAC

CCGAAAAGCCGCGGCTTAACTAACGTGCCACCAGC
CCCCGGTAATTACGTTAGGTGGCAAGGCGTTTTCC
GGAAATTTATTGGGGCCATAAAAGCCCCGCCAGGT
GGTTTTCTTTAGGTCTGGATGGGGAAAACCCCCGG
GCCTCAACCCGGGGGAGGGGTCCATAGGGAAAACG
GGGGAAAACCTTGAGGGGCAGAAAAGAGTA

[lactis. hb27](#)

[Lactobacillus
casei strain](#)

[KF011266.1](#)

[Lactobacillus sp. BBT91](#)

[FJ981911.1](#)

[Lactobacillus sp. strain
H10WTRM5](#)

[MH985183.1](#)

06

GGTTTCAGTCATAGATTGACTGGCTCAGGTGCGGTGG
GACCCCTAAGAGTTTACTGGCTCGGGCGGTGG
GTCACCCCTTTAAATTTGACCCGGCCCCGGTGG
GGGAAACCCTCCATTAAAGGTTAACCTTTGAACCG
CATGGTTCAAATTGAAAAAGGGCTTCGGCTGTACT
TATGGATGGACCCGCGTCGATAAGCTAGTTGGTGAG
GTAACGGCTACCAAGGCAACGATGCGTAGCCCGAC
CTGAGAGGGTGATCGGCCACTCTGGGACTGAGACAC
GGCCAGACTCCTACGGGGGGCAGCGTAGGGGAATC
TTCCGATTGGAGGAAAGTCTGACGGAACAACGCCG
GTGGAGTGAGGAAGGCTTTCGGGTCGTAAGGGAGG
GGTGGTAGGGAACAATTCTAGTTGAATAGCTGGCA
CCTTGGGGGAAACCTAACCGGAAAGCCACGGTTAAT
CATCCACCCACCCCGGGAAATACTAAGGTGCCCA
CCTTTATGGGGAAATGATTGCGCCTTAAAGCCGGCG
CGAGTGGGATTTTTTAAAGTCCGGTTGGGAAAGCCCC
ACGGCCTCAACCCGTGGAGGGGTCATTGGAAACTTGC
GAGAACTTTGAGGTGCAAAGGGACAA

08

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GGGGGGTCCCCCTTTAAAGTTACCCTCGCCAG
GGGGGGTTTTAAATAATAAAAAAAAAAATTCGCCTGC
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GACCTGCCAGGGTGATCGGCCACACTGGGAAGTGGC
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CGCGTGGGGTGGGAGGTTTTTCGGGTGCGAAAACCCG
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GGGGGCCACCCGCGCGTAATAGTAGGTGGGGAGCT
TTTTCCCGATTTTTGGGTGCTTAAGGCGG

[Lactobacillus lactis](#)

[strain A7c](#)

[KC936159.1](#)

[Lactobacillus fermenti](#)

[strain A7b](#)

[KC936158.1](#)

[Lactobacillus casei
strain NIOER227](#)

[MG205948.1](#)

[Lactobacillus lactis
strain OU13](#)

[KJ26301.1](#)

07

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GACCACCCCTTTATAGTTTACTGGCCCGGGTGGC
TTGGACCTCCCCCTTATAACTTATAGTTTGGGATAACT
CCGGAAACCGGGGCTAATACCGAATAATCTGTTTCA
CCTCATGGTGAAATATTGAAAGACGGTTTCGGCTGTC
GCTATAGGATGGGCCCCGCGGCATTAGCTAGTTGGT
GAGGTAACGGCTACCAAGGCGACGATGCGTAGCCG
ACCTGAGAGGGTGATCGGCCACACTGGGACTGAGAC
ACGGCCCAGACTCCTACGGGAGGCAGCAGTAGGGAA
TCTTCCACAATGGGCGAAAGCCTGATGGAGCAACGCC
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GTGCCAGCAGCCGCTAATACGTAAGGTGGCAAGCG
TTGTCCGGGAATTATTGGCGTAAGCGCGCAGGTGC
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TAACCGATGAGTGCTACGGTCTATGGTATCCGCCCTA
TTAA

09

CGTCATCCACGGTAGACATGGCTCAGGTGCGCTTGGC
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CCAGACTCCTACGGGAGGCAGCAGTAGGGAATCTTCC
GCAATGGACGAAAGTCTGACGGAGCAACGCCGCGTG
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AGGGAAGAACAAGTGTAGTTGAATAAGCTGGCACC
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AAGTGAATTCATGTGTAGCGATGAATTGCGTAGAGA
TATGAGACACAGTGCAGGGGACTTCTGACTGTAAGT
GACTGAGGCGCGAAAGCGTGGTGAGCAACCAGAA
TAGATACCATGCTAGTCCACGCTTACGATGAGTGCT
ACTATACAGGGATCGCCTTAGTGCTGAGTAACGCATA
GGACCTCGCTGGATTACGCGCGTAAGTTCTGCAC

[Lactobacillus sp.](#)

[strain 90.2.13](#)

[KX649151.1](#)

[Lactobacillus casei](#)

[FN31](#)

[DQ462190.1](#)

10

GGACCCTCCTCCGGTTGACTGGCTCAGGTGCGGTGGG
ACCCCTAAGAGTTTACTGGCCCGGGGGGTTTGT
TCCCCCTTAAAAGTTTAAAGACTGGGCCAGGTCCGG
GGAACCGACTAATAAAGGATAACATTTTGAACCGC
ATGGTTCGAAATTGAAAGGCGGCTTCGGCTGTCCCTT

ATGGATGGACCCGCGTCGCATTAGCTAGTTGGTGAGG
TAACGGCTCACCAAGGCAACGATGCGTAGCCGACCTG
AGAGGGTGATCGGCCACACTGGGACTGAGACACGGC
CCAGACTCCTACGGGAGGCAGCAGTAGGGAATCTTCC
GCAATGGACGAAAGTCCTGACGGAGCAACGCCGCGT
GAGTGATGAAGGCTTTTCGGGTGCTAAAACCTGTTG
TTAGGGAAGAACAAGTGCTAGTTGAAATAGGCTGGC
CCCTTGACGGGTACCCTAACCAGAAAAGCCACGGCTA
ACTACGTTGCCACCAGCCCCGCGTAATACGTAGGGG
GCAAAGCGTTTATCCGGGAATTTTTGGGGCGTAAAG
CCGCGCCGACGGTGGTTTTCTTAAGTTCTGAATGTG
AAGCCCCACGGGCTTCAACCCTTGGGAGGGGTTTATT
TGGAAAAACTGGGAAAAATTTGGAGTGCCAGAAAAGA
GGGAAAAGGTGGAATTTTCTTTGTGGAAGCGGGT
TGAAAAATGCCACAAAAGAAGTATTTTGGAGAGGAAA
CACTCAGGTGGTCAAAGGGCGAATTTTTTCGGGGCC
TGGTAACTCTAGACACCTTGGAGGCGCGCCGAACAC
GCGTGGGGTGAGGGCACACCCGAGGAGTATGAGAT
ACCCGCTGAGTATATGCTCACACACGCGCGCTGTTA
CACACGAGAGTGAGAGGTGCGCTTCAACAGGTGCTTA
TAGAGAGCGATATTTTCCAGGCCTCATCTATGTCACG
AGCTGC

[Lactobacillus sp. strain
H10WTRM5](#)

[MH985183.1](#)

11

AGGGTTTAGTCTATAATTGCCGTGGCTCAGTTGCGCTT
GGTTCGCCTTTATATGTTCGAGTGGCGGACGGGTGAGT
AATGTCTGGGAACTGCCTGATGGAGGGGGATAACT
ACTGAAAACGGTAGCTAATACCGCATAACGTCGCAA
GACCAAAGAGGGGGACCTTCGGGCCTCTTGCCATCAG
ATGTGCCAGATGGGATTAGCTAGTAGGTGGGGTAAAC
GGCTCACCTAGGCGACGATCCCTAGCTGGTCTGAGAG
GATGACCAGCCACACTGGAACCTGAGACACGGTCCAG
ACTCCTACGGGAGGCAGCAGTGGGGAATATTGCACA
ATGGGCGCAAGCCTGATGCAGCCATGCCGCGTGTATG
AAGAAGGCCTTCGGTTGTAAATACTTTACGCGGGGA
GGAAGGCGTAAGGTTAATAACCCTTGTTCGATTGACGT
AACC CGCAAGAGCCCGGGTAACCTCGTGCCGGCAGC
CGCGGTAATCCGGAGGGTGCAGCGTTAATCGAATTAC
TGGCGTAAGCCCGCAGGCGTCTTTCAAGCCGATGTAA
ATCCCGGGGCAACCTGGGACTGATTGCAACTGGCGGC
TAGGTCTGTAAGGGTACATTCCGTTACGTGAATGCCA
AACTGGAGATCCGTGGAGGCTCCCTGAAAACCTGGCT
AATCCAAGGTGGGCACATAGATTATCTGGATCCCGGA
ACGTCCATAAGAGTGCCTAGTGGATCAGATACCGGTA
TCACCCTGTAATCGCCGGGGTAAAAACC

[Streptococcus sp
Z21](#)

[KF835734.1](#)

12

CGTCAAATTAAGCAAACGTTTCATGGCTCAGGTGCGTT
TGGATCTCGCCCTAATAGTTTTAGCGGCGGACGGTTG
AGTAACACGTGCTTCTCTGCCATAAAGACTGGGATA
ACTCCGGAAACCGGGGCTAATACCGGATAACATTTT
GAACCGCATGGTTGAAATTTGAAAGGCGGCTTCGGCT
GTCACTTATGGATGGACCCGCGTGCATAGTACTGTT
GGTGAGGTAACGGCTCACCAAGGCAACGATGCGTAG
CCGACCTGAGAGGGTATCGGCCACACTGGGACTGA
GACACGGCCAGACTCCTACGGGAGGCAGCAGTAGG
GAATCTCCGCAATGGACGAAAGTCTGACGGAGCAA
CGCCGCGTGAGTGATGAAGGCTTTTCGGGTGCTAAAAC
TCTGTTGTTAGGGAAGAACAAGTGCTAGTTGAATAAG
CTGGCACCTTGACGGTACCTAACCAGAAAGCCACGGC

TAACTACGTGCCAGCAGCCGCGGTAATACGTAGGTGG
CAAGCGTTATCCGGAAGTTATTGGGCGTAAAGCGCGC
GCAGGTGGCTTTCTTAGTCTGATGTGAAGGCCACCG
CTCATCCGTGGAGGGTCATTGTACTGGGAGACTTGAG
TGCAGAGAGGAAGTGCATTCCATGTGTAGCGGTGAAT
GGCGTACAGATATGGAGGACACCAGTGGGCCGAGGG
CGACTTCTGACTGTAACCTGAACTGAGGTGCGCCGAA
CGCGTGGGGAGCAACAGATAAGTACCTTGCAAGATC
CACGCCGTTAAACGATGAGGTGCTAACGTGTAAAGA
CGCTTCCGCCCTTACGTGCAAGTACGCATAGGCATT
C

[Lactobacillus sp.
C02](#)

[MN595199.1](#)

[Lactobacillus sp
strain B12](#)

[MG950219.1](#)

13

AGGGTCACTCCTTCGCGTGTCTGGCTCAGGTGCGGTT
GAATCACTTCTTATAGTTTACGCGCGGCTCACGGGT
GATTAATGTCCGCCTTTATGCCCGATAGAGGGGGATA
ACTACTGGAAACGGTGGCTAATACCGCATGACGTCTA
CGGACCAAAGCAGGGGCTCTTCGGACCTTGCCTATC
GGATGAACCCATATGGGATTAGCTAGTAGGTGAGGTA
AAGGCTCACCTAGGCGACGATCTCTAGCTGGTCTGAG
AGGATGATCAGCCACACTGGGACTGAGACACGGCCC
AGACTCCTACGGGAGGCAGCAGTGGGGAATATTGCA
CAATGGGCGCAAGCCTGATGCAGCCATGCCGCGTGT
TGAAGAAGGCCTTAGGGTTGTAAAGTACTTTACGCGG
GGAGGAAGGTGATAAAGTTAATACCTTTATCATTGAC
GTTACCCGCGAAGAGCAGCCGGCTAACTCCGTGCCAG
CGCCGCGTTATACGGAGGGTGCAGCGTTAATCGAAT
TACTGGCGTAAGCGCACGCGGCGGCTAATAGTCTAG
ATTGAAGCCCGAGCTAACTGGGAATGCATCTGAAACT
GGTTGCTAAGCCTTGGAGAGGGGTAGAATTCATGTTTA
GCGCGAAATGCTAAATTGGCAGAATTCGGTGGCGAG
GCGGCCCTGGACAAGACTGGCCTCGGTCCAATCGTG
CGGGATAGGATAGACCCTGGTATTACCGGAACATT
ATTAAGGTTGGCCTGACGGGCTTCGGGCTACGGTAAT
CACCCCTGGAGACGGCCCAAGT

[Proteus sp. strain P211.1](#)

[Proteus sp. strain LMRE72](#)

[Proteus penneri strain 2-63](#)

15

GGCATCTCTTATAGGTGACTGGCTCAGGTGCGCTGG
GCCCCCTTTATATTTTACCTGGGCCCGGGGGGTT
GGTCTCCCCCTTAAAATTTTACCTGGGCCAGGTCC
GGGGAACCCCCCTAAAAAGAATAATCTGTTTACC
TCATGGTGAAATATTGAAAGACGGTTTTCCGCTGTCCG
TATAGGATGGGCCCGCGGCCATTAGCTAGTTGGTGA
GGTAACGGCTACCAAGGCGACGATGCGTAGCCGAC
CTGAGAGGGTATCGGCCACACTGGGACTGAAACAC
GGCCAGACTCCTACGGGAGGCAGCAGTAGGGAATC
TTCCACAATGGGGCGAAAGCCTGATGGAGCACCGCCC
GCGTGAGTGAAGAAGGATTTCCGTTTCGAAAACCTG
TTGTAAGGGAAGAACAAGTTACGTAGTAACTGGCTGT
ACCTTGACGGTACCTTATTAGAAAGGCCACGGCTAAC
TACGTTCCAGCAGCCGCGGTAATACGTAGGTGGCAA
GCGTTGTCGGAATTATTGGGCGTAAAGCGCGCGCAG
GTGGTTTCTTAAGTCTGATGGTGAAAGCCACGCTCA
ACCGTGAGGGTCATTTGAAACGGGAGACTTGAGTGC

AGAAGAGGATGTGGAATTCCAGTGTACCGATGAATTG
CGTACAGATTGGAAGAAACACAGTGGCGAAGCGACT
ATCTGGTCTTGTACTGACACTGAGCTGGAAAGCGTGG
GAGCAACAGGAATGAGATTCCCTGGAGTTTACGCCG
TTAACGAATGAGGGCTAACCGGTGAGAGTGGTACGTC
CGTAGTTTGTATGGCCACGGTTAAGTGCATATAATG
AACACT

[Lactococcus sp strain](#) [KF261018.1](#)

[Lactococcus sp strain](#)
[SB2.124](#) [JQ744631.1](#)

16

CGTCCACTCTTAAGATTGACATGGCTCAGGTGCGCTG
GACCCCCCTTAAGAGTTTACTGGGCCCGGGGGGGT
GGGTCCCCCTTTAAATTTAACCTGGGCCCGGGGG
GGGGGACCCCCCTTAAAAAGTTTAACTTTTGCAC
CGCATGGTTCGAAATTGATAGGCGGCTTCGGCTGTCA
CTTATGGATGGACCCGCGTCGCATTAGCTAGTTGGTG
AGGTAACGGCTACCAAGGCAACGATGCGTAGCCGA
CCTGAGAGGGTGATCGGCCACACTGGGACTGAGACA
CGGCCAGACTCCTACGGGGAGGCAGCAGTAGGGAA
TCTTCCGCAATGGACGAAAGTCTGACGGAGCAACGC
CGCGTGAGGTGATGAAGGGTTTTCGGGTCGTA AAAAC
TCTGTTGTTAGGGGAAGAACAAGTGCTAGTTTGAATA
AGCTGGCACCTTGACGGGTACCTAAACCAGAAAGCC
ACGGGCTAACTACGGTGCCAGCCAGCCGGTAAAA
ACGTAGGTGGCAAGCGTTTATCCGGAATTATTTGGGG
CGTAAAAGCGCGCGCAGGTGGGTTTCTTTAAGTTCTG
AATGTGGAAGGCCCGGCTTCACCCGTGGAGGGGT
CTTTGGAAAACCTGGGAACTTGAGTGGCGGAGAGA
GGGAAAGTGGGATTTTCCATGGTGTACCAGGTGGAAA
TTGCGTAGAGATATTGGAGGAAACCCAGTGGGC
AGAAGGGCGAATTTTTCCGGGTCTGTGTAACCTGAAC
TCTTGAGGCCCCGAAACGCGGTGGTGTGAGCCAAACA
GGATTAATATACCCCTGGTGTAGTTCCACCGCCCCGT
TACACGAGATGTGAGTGTCTAATCTGTTTAGAGGA
GATCTTCTCCGCTCTCCTCTATTATAGTGGCGTGGAGG
AGATTTAAGCACGCCATTATTTAGGGACCTTCTATCC
GCGCTGTGTGGGAGAAGTGATTTCGCAATCTGCGC

[Lactobacillus lactis](#)
[strain SSe2 1](#) [KF741359.1](#)

[Lactobacillus sp strain](#)
[NIOER5 1](#) [MG205787.1](#)

17

AGGGTTCAGTCTAAGGATTGACATGGCTCAGGTGCGC
TTGGATCACCCCTTAGAGTTTGACCGGGCTCGGGGG
CGTTGGGTCCCCCTTTATAGTTTACCTGGCCCCAGG
GCTGAAAACGATGGCTCTTAAACATACTCTCTCAGG
AGCAAAGCGGGGACTTCGGTCTTGCCTATCGGAT
GAACCCATATGGGGATTAGCTAGTAGGGGGGGTAAT
GGCTCACCTAGGCGACGATCCCTAGCTGGTCTGGGGA
GATGATCAGCCACACTGGGACTGAGACACGGGCC
AACTCCTACGGGGAGGCAGCAGTGGGGGAATATTG
CACAATGGGCGCAAGCCCTGGATGCACCCCTGCCGCG
TGTATTGAAAGAAGGCCCTAGGTTGAAAAGTACTTT
TCAGTCGGGAGGAAAGGCGTTTGTATGCTTATTATCTT
CCAAGGATTGGCGTTACCCAAGGAAAAAGCACCCGG
TTACCTCCTTGCCAGGGGGCCGCGGAAATCCGGAG
GGTGCTAGCGTTTATTGGAATTTCTTGGGGCGTAAAC
CCCCCCCCGGGGTTAATTAATTAATTTGAAACCCC
CCGGGGTGAAGCCGGGGAATGGAATTTGA

[Proteus sp strain](#)
[JVSP1](#) [KR108920.1](#)

PLATE 1: Showing the bacterial PCR gel.
19-20

Lactic acid bacteria isolated from locally made 'nono' includes *Lactobacillus lactis*, *Lactococcus sp*, *Streptococcus sp* which is in agreement with Akabanda *et al.*, 2014. The molecular characterization shows that *Lactobacillus*, *Lactococcus* *Streptococcus spp.* dominate the natural microbial flora in the locally produced nono by the Hausa/Fulani women that hawked this product Adesokan *et al.*, 2011; Cisem, 2003.

Lactobacillus sp is widely known for their ability to utilize lactose in milk to produce lactic acid which eventually lowers the pH. The ability to ferment Lactose makes *Lactobacillus spp* an important organisms which can serve as starter culture for the production of "Nono". The lactic acid produced also helps to preserve the food (Marino *et al.*; 2003). *Lactococcus spp* also produces lactic acid from lactose, but at a much slower rate than *Lactobacillus spp*, which makes the latter a better starter culture. Though other metabolic products produced by *Lactococcus spp* contribute to flavour and aroma of the milk products (Marino *et al.*; 2003

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